

LOD-GEOSS Deliverable D6+D7

Demonstration and Best Practices

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1 Introduction

One of the central aims of the LOD-GEOSS project has been the development of a FAIR (Wilkinson et al. 2016) data infrastructure within the research domain of energy systems analysis. With this document we want to show some example how the built up infrastructure, which is described in Deliverable D3 (Frey et al. 2023), can be used to improve data sharing within the research domain.

These demonstrators focus on different aspects. The first demonstrator "Shared Technology Data" takes a small piece of data, a dataset which characterizes wind turbines in different future years and shows how this dataset can be set up to be annotated with the Open Energy Ontology (Booshehri et al. 2021), uploaded into the Open Energy Platform and registered to the energy Databus. There it can be discovered by the search features, downloaded and used by different energy system models.

The second example focuses on publishing and finding a scenario dataset. The data needs to be annotated, uploaded to an open data repository and can then be found by a semantic search.

The tools are also useful for building modeling chains. The model coupling demonstrator shows how different models can produce results, share them on the Open Energy Platform and the energy databus and these results can be used by a second model to analyse the impacts of the different modeling results in the first step. The open publication and registration of the datasets in the model workflow increases the transparency of the modeling pipeline and increases the reproducibility of the performed research.

The Global Earth Observation System of Systems (GEOSS) offers a vast amount of meteorological data, which can be used in energy systems analysis. The GEOSS demonstrator shows the use of wind speed data from numerical reanalysis and the incorporation of this data into an energy systems model.

The next example shows a model workflow by the regional energy system model oemof-B3 where the infrastructure is used to improve the documentation of the workflows and to increase the transparency and reproducibility of the model workflow.

The main tasks as annotation and publication of data, searching data are documented in a separate chapter, as they appear in similar form in many of the examples.

The report is wrapped up with a short best practice descriptions on how to reuse the examples in other contexts, how to apply to apply them to ones own modeling works and pipelines.

2 Data Infrastructure Building Blocks

The LOD-GEOSS project aims to enable efficient and high quality energy system research by linking open data. For this purpose, the pursued project approach focuses on the development and establishment of a distributed database infrastructure that supports the identification, traceability, reuse and improvement of energy systems research data. In this chapter, the main components of such an infrastructure are introduced (cf. figure 2.1).

2.1 Metadata Standards and Ontologies

Metadata is data that describes a dataset. Metadata is defined as the data providing information about one or more aspects of the data; it is used to summarize basic information about data which can make tracking and working with specific data easier. These information describe e.g. the name and content of the dataset, the publisher and contributors of the dataset and the license of it. Metadata can have various forms that’s why setting a metadata standard for one domain is necessary. A metadata schema is a standardised template which suggests the aspects that should be described about the data. The metadata is a separate construct from the dataset itself which is saved as a separate data for example in a .json or .xml format.

In the energy system domain the metadata is typically created when a dataset should be published and is not used before this step. In the energy domain there is a metadata standard from the Open Energy Platform which is openly available. When describing the content of the dataset, especially the column headers, a joint vocabulary of the energy domain e.g. provided by the Open Energy Ontology can be used. Linking the column headers of the dataset with

Figure 2.1: Main components of a distributed data infrastructure.

the Ontology through the metadata gives additional information with a clear definition of the data content and makes the data easily findable. So the overall goal of metadata is informing about the data and making the data findable, when it is saved on an openly available platform like the OEP or Zenodo.

2.2 Repository: OEP

In order to improve the visibility, communication and transparency in energy system modelling, the Open Energy Platform¹ has been established as a place to share and discover common definitions, model descriptions and results data in a standardized way. The platform provides a language-independent interface on top of the Open Energy Database. It has the goal to be intuitive and easy to use to achieve a wide adoption in the field. Further, the visual and understandable presentation of datasets should facilitate the access and discovery of the datasets while offering automated access of the data with the help of a RESTful HTTP-interface. All contributors publish datasets under an open license so that the barrier towards reproduction and incorporation into other work is as low as possible.

The database management system that underlies the OEP is PostgreSQL. This means that data that is uploaded on the platform needs to have a tabular data model with columns and rows. However, functionalities of SQL like primary/foreign key pairs are also available on the Platform.

The process of uploading data to the OEP is described in detail in Section 8.1.

2.3 Databus Platform

The DBpedia Databus² is a platform to capture invested effort by data consumers who need better data quality (fitness for use) in order to use the data and give improvements back to the data source and other consumers. DBpedia Databus enables anybody to build an automated DBpedia-style extraction, mapping and testing for any data they need. Instead of hosting data, the platform registers their descriptions and references the original data sources and their extracted or cleaned derivatives. It allows to attribute rich meta-data to an entry. Meta-data entries can be linked to ontologies to use common definitions of the field. Further, queries to the platform can be performed with SPARQL.

¹<https://openenergy-platform.org/>

²<https://databus.dbpedia.org/>

3 Using shared data

3.1 Challenges

Energy system models usually need some data to describe some technology characteristics, like investment cost, efficiencies, space requirements. A data source which is widely used are the technology data reports from the Danish Energy Agency. The technology data is a data catalog for technological energy system modeling data regularly published by the Danish Energy Agency. It spans multiple energy sectors, such as electricity generation, heating, transport and industry and energy storage and transport data, split in different data sheets. Within its scope, the catalog includes a wide range of technology parameters that have relevance in energy systems modeling. The catalog stands out in the domain due to its coverage of various technologies (incumbent and emerging) and its regular maintenance and updates. Thus, we identified it as a good fit to draw on an excerpt of the catalog as an example to demonstrate the developed technologies in this project. Here we choose as an example the technology dataset for onshore wind power generation from the report of electricity generation and district heating ([Danish Energy Agency and Energinet 2020](#)). The report contains a typical table of such data:

Technology	Large wind turbines on land										
Year of final investment decision	2015	2020	2030	2040	2050	Uncertainty(2020)		Uncertainty(2050)		Note	Ref
Energy/technical data						Lower	Upper	Lower	Upper		
Generating Capacity for one unit (MW)	3.1	4.2	5	5.5	6	2.0	6.0	1.5	8.0	A1	3
Average annual full-load hours	3100	3400	3600	3700	3800	2000	4000	2000	4500	A,L	3
Forced outage (%)	3.0%	2.5%	2.0%	1.8%	1.5%	1.0%	5.0%	1.0%	5.0%	B	4
Planned outage (%)	0.3%	0.3%	0.3%	0.3%	0.3%	0.1%	0.5%	0.1%	0.5%	C	4
Technical lifetime (years)	25	27	30	30	30	25	35	25	40	D	14
Construction time (years)	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1	3	1	3	E	4
Space requirement (1000m ² /MW)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	F	
...											

Table 3.1: Excerpt from an onshore wind power data sheet in the technology data report([Danish Energy Agency and Energinet 2020](#), page 224)

Looking at the data from table 3.1 shows several difficulties. Human readers are used to put the labels in the first row and the consecutive data lines towards

the right. This is not how databases are usually organized. Usually, tables in a relational database have a header in the first row with the names and definitions of the column below and all remaining rows after contain the data records. Next, the table is not regularly organized, there are several grouped cells in the table which creates an irregular structure of the data. On the right-hand side there are additional columns with notes and references, which break the structure of columns which give the data for different years.

Futhermore, using the catalog entails licensing issues when it comes to right of use and the republication of results. The catalog is comprised of many different data source, which are referenced within each technology data sheet. The referencing does not always meet the minimum standards of scientific citation, which makes it unfeasible to clarify underlying terms of use for each data source. Moreover, the Danish Energy Agency does not provide a license for each data sheet itself.

As our aim in our demonstrators was to publish clearly licensed and open datasets, we asked the Danish Energy Agency for permission to republish an extract under an open license, which they granted us in writing.

In this demonstrator we want to base the modeling of onshore wind power with the same data source. Once this example has been reorganized, annotated and uploaded to the Open Energy Platform, different energy systems download the data and convert and merge it into their input data. Before we look into the workflow we want to give a brief introduction into the involved models.

3.2 ETHOS.FINE

The *Framework for Integrated Energy System Assessment* from the *Energy Transformation Pathway Optimization Suite* (ETHOS.FINE)¹ is an open source python package which provides a framework for modeling, optimizing and assessing energy systems (Welder et al. 2018). With the provided framework, systems with multiple regions, commodities and time steps can be modeled. The objective of the framework is the minimization of the total annual cost while considering technical and environmental constraints. In addition to its modeling capabilities, FINE offers methods for temporal and spatial aggregation to reduce model complexity and computation times.

The model structure can be set-up within a Python script by consecutively adding component blocks for generation, demand, conversion, storage and transport to the model. A typical input of an energy system model in FINE consists of a list of locations and corresponding time-series in hourly resolution for energy demand and potential renewable generation. In addition, techno-economic parameters for the available components need to be defined. These contain values like conversion factors, storage losses as well as investment, operation and maintenance costs.

The FINE framework creates an optimization model which is then solved for minimal annualized costs. The model output after optimization consists of

¹<https://github.com/FZJ-IEK3-VSA/FINE>

optimal values for the siting, design and operation of the components together with the resulting costs per component.

3.3 REMix

The REMix framework models future energy systems with high spatial and temporal resolution based on a linear optimization algorithm to minimize system costs. It can model a wide range of technologies for the conversion, storage and transport of energy in the electricity, heat, gas and transport sectors from a central planner's point of view, taking into account numerous techno-economic constraints. Besides the hourly dispatch over one year, the capacities of all considered technologies can be optimized under perfect foresight. REMix consists of a collection of mutually compatible source codes that can be combined in a modular fashion. By reusing the same modeling concepts, different research questions can be addressed based on a common set of available model features so as to simplify understanding and maintenance. Implemented in the mathematical programming language GAMS, the core of the framework is embedded in a Python environment. The comprehensive framework was developed for studies in the field of energy system analysis, with typical use cases being the modeling of competition between technologies and the solution of transport and storage problems.

The REMix input dataset includes, on the one hand, scalar data for the techno-economic description of technologies as well as overarching scalars such as emission factors and CO₂ budgets etc. and, on the other hand, time series of available renewable energy resources, but also as technical boundary conditions. The model is parameterized using Python scripts to configure the technologies in a data-driven manner. For this purpose, the input data is read in from different sources or databases and transformed into data frames of a specific format. The data is then automatically converted into an user defined tabular data format, for example csv.

In addition to the system costs resulting from the objective function, the model output includes the optimized capacities of all technologies and their deployment together with the associated costs. Furthermore, emissions and marginal costs for the individual commodities are provided in the result file. Finally, general plotting functions facilitate the interpretation of the results for the user.

3.4 Open Energy System Modelling Framework (oemof)

Oemof stands for Open Energy System Modelling Framework and is a Python-based framework for energy system analysis initiated by ZNES Flensburg, RLI Berlin and OvGU Magdeburg which is used, developed and maintained by several institutes. The framework is published on GitHub under an Open Source licence and allows the creation of simulation and optimisation models. The optimisation library oemof.solph enables dispatch and investment optimisation. The electrical grid can be modeled in a transshipment or a linear optimal

power flow approach. Other libraries that are able to generate feed-in or synthetic demand timeseries can be used to complement oemof.solph, e.g. to generate input data for an optimisation model.

3.5 Workflow

3.5.1 Publication of data in the Open Energy Platform

The first step to make this data usable is therefore a transformation of the dataset to be able to ingest it into the database of the open energy platform and ease the annotation of the dataset. An excerpt of the transformed dataset can be seen in table 3.2². The individual data fields are now in the columns and the data records appears as lines.

id	data	generating_capacity	average_annual_fullload_hours	forced_outage	planned_outage	technical_lifetime	construction_time	space_requirement	...
1	2015	3.1	3100	3.0%	0.3%	25	1.5	-	
2	2020	4.2	3400	2.5%	0.3%	27	1.5	-	
3	2030	5.0	3600	2.0%	0.3%	30	1.5	-	
4	2040	5.5	3700	1.8%	0.3%	30	1.5	-	
5	2050	6.0	3800	1.5%	0.3%	30	1.5	-	
6	uncertainty_2020_lower	2	2000	1.0%	0.1%	25	1	-	
7	uncertainty_2020_upper	6	4000	5.0%	0.5%	35	3	-	
6	uncertainty_2050_lower	1.5	2000	1.0%	0.1%	25	1	-	
7	uncertainty_2050_upper	8.0	4500	5.0%	0.5%	40	3	-	

Table 3.2: Excerpt from the transformed table of table 3.1

With this clearer structure, the data can now be annotated with the Open Energy Metadatastring and the Open Energy Ontology Booshehri et al. (2021). To be able to use the open energy ontology, a number of new terms needed to be defined in the Open Energy Ontology: full load hours, forced outage, planned outage, space requirement, net capacity factor, planned availability, unplanned availability, equipment cost, grid connection cost, rent of land cost, decommissioning cost, rotor diameter, hub height, specific power, lifetime, construction time. According to the contribution guideline³ from the Open Energy Ontology, issues were created for all these terms and the workflow of the guideline was followed until the definitions have been agreed and terms had been implemented in the Open Energy Ontology. At this point, the dataset is ready to be annotated with the Open Energy Metadatastring and to be uploaded to the Open Energy Platform.

The listing 3.1 contains the metadata string for the annotation of the onshore wind technology data.

The line gives the data a name followed by a human readable title. The id is a unique id for the data set, here the URL to the data set is used. The description contains a human readable description of the data set. Lines 6 and 7 indicate the language of the dataset

Starting on line 9 the subject of the dataset is given. The subject is annotated with the Open Energy Ontology. Name contains the human readable display name of the ontology, the path in line 12 is the URI of the ontology entry.

²https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/view/model_draft/wind_turbine_onshore_lod_geoss.tp

³<https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/ontology/blob/dev/CONTRIBUTING.md>

Lines 15 through 23 give a list of keywords for the dataset. Lines 24 through 33 give context information on the publisher, the project context, funding organization and funding contract related information.

Lines 34 to 46 give information about the spatial context, here the data set is valid for Europe and contains data from 2015 to 2050 in 10 year time steps.

Lines 51 to 82 give the source of the dataset. Here the reports and data sheets of the Danish Energy Agency are referenced.

Lines 83 to 91 give the current license of this data set and how the license can be used,

Lines 92 to 128 describe the contributors to this data set what they have done with the data set. This improves the traceability of changes to the dataset.

Starting from Line 129 is the resources section which describes the table in a machine readable way in more detail. The first lines indicate that it is a table, on the open energy platform on a PostgreSQL database. The schema is described after the "schema" key. There is a list of "fields" which describe each data column. Taking "generating capacity" starting at line 191 as an example: name is the name of the column, description is a human readable description, the data type is real number. The isAbout links the data column to a concept of the an ontology. Name is is the display name of the ontology key and path is the URI to the ontology key. The definition of a column is finalized with its unit. These definitions and links enable machines to interpret the data.

The metadata is finished with some information about the version of the metadata itself and some comments.

```

1 {
2   "name": "rli_dea_td_generation_wind_turbine",
3   "title": "RLI - Danish Energy Agency - Technology Data for
4     Generation of Electricity and District Heating - Technology
5     Data Catalogue for Electricity and district heating
6     production - Updated April 2020 - Wind Turbine (Selected
7     Parameter)",
8   "id": "http://openenergyplatform.org/dataedit/view/model_draft/
9     rli_dea_td_generation_wind_turbine",
10  "description": "This Technology Data catalogue includes
11    technology data for technologies for centralized and
12    decentralized production of electricity and district heat.
13    Technology data concerns more or less mature technologies.
14    There is currently one combined Technology Data catalogue
15    concerning generation of electricity and district heating.
16    The catalogue was first published in August 2016, and is
17    updated continuously. Technology descriptions in the previous
18    catalogue from May 2012 have now been included in the
19    catalogue from 2016 although some are not updated since 2015.
20    It is mentioned in the beginning of the specific chapters,
21    when each technology has been updated the last time. Index:
22    20 Wind turbines on-shore (updated May 2019) On-shore
23    turbines and Domestic turbines. 21 Wind turbines off-shore (
24    updated May 2019) Off-shore turbines and Near shore turbines
25    (minor adjustment September 2019).",
26  "language": [
27    "en-GB"
28  ],
29  "subject": [

```

```
10  {
11    "name": "wind energy converting unit",
12    "path": "https://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeo/
        OEO_00000044"
13  }
14 ],
15 "keywords": [
16   "CC-BY-4.0",
17   "Danish Energy Agency",
18   "Review",
19   "Technology Data Catalogue",
20   "RLI",
21   "Wind",
22   "OEO"
23 ],
24 "publicationDate": "2022-02-11",
25 "context": {
26   "homepage": "https://reiner-lemoine-institut.de/lod-geoss/",
27   "sourceCode": "https://github.com/LOD-GEOSS",
28   "contact": "https://github.com/Ludee",
29   "grantNo": "03EI1005D",
30   "fundingAgency": "Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und
        Klimaschutz",
31   "fundingAgencyLogo": "https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:
        BMWi_Logo_2021.svg#/media/File:BMWi_Logo_2021.svg",
32   "publisherLogo": "https://reiner-lemoine-institut.de/wp-content
        /uploads/2015/09/rlilogo.png"
33 },
34 "spatial": {
35   "extent": "Europe"
36 },
37 "temporal": {
38   "referenceDate": "2015-01-01",
39   "timeseries": [
40     {
41       "start": "2015-10-05",
42       "end": "2050-10-05",
43       "resolution": "10 years"
44     }
45   ]
46 },
47 "review": {
48   "path": "https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/data-
        preprocessing/issues/92",
49   "badge": "Platinum"
50 },
51 "sources": [
52   {
53     "title": "Danish Energy Agency - Technology Data",
54     "description": "The Danish Energy Agency and Energinet publish
        catalogues of technology data for energy technologies.
        Technology Data provides information about technology,
        economy and environment for a number of energy
        installations and are among other things used by the Danish
        Energy Agency for energy projections.",
55     "path": "https://ens.dk/en/our-services/projections-and-models/
        technology-data",
```



```
56  "licenses": [  
57    {  
58      "attribution": "@ Danish Energy Agency 2021"  
59    }  
60  ],  
61 },  
62 {  
63   "title": "Danish Energy Agency - Technology Data for Generation  
        of Electricity and District Heating",  
64   "description": "TThis Technology Data catalogue includes  
        technology data for technologies for centralized and  
        decentralized production of electricity and district heat.  
        Technology data concerns more or less mature technologies  
        .",  
65   "path": "https://ens.dk/en/our-services/projections-and-models/  
        technology-data/technology-data-generation-electricity-and  
        ",  
66   "licenses": [  
67     {  
68       "attribution": "@ Danish Energy Agency 2021"  
69     }  
70   ],  
71 },  
72 {  
73   "title": "Technology Data Catalogue for Electricity and  
        district heating production - Updated April 2020",  
74   "description": "Data collection for electricity generation and  
        district heating plants, last update: April 2020",  
75   "path": "https://ens.dk/sites/ens.dk/files/Analyser/  
        technology_data_for_el_and_dh.xlsx",  
76   "licenses": [  
77     {  
78       "attribution": "@ Danish Energy Agency 2021"  
79     }  
80   ],  
81 }  
82 ],  
83 "licenses": [  
84   {  
85     "instruction": "You are free: To Share, To Create, To Adapt; As  
        long as you: Attribute! See: https://tldrlegal.com/license  
        /creative-commons-attribution-4.0-international-(cc-by-4)",  
86     "attribution": "@ Danish Energy Agency @ Reiner Lemoine  
        Institut",  
87     "name": "CC-BY-4.0",  
88     "title": "Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International",  
89     "path": "https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/legalcode"  
90   }  
91 ],  
92 "contributors": [  
93   {  
94     "title": "Christoph Muschner",  
95     "email": "christoph.muschner@rl-institut.de",  
96     "object": "metadata",  
97     "comment": "Transpose the original table",  
98     "date": "2021-06-29"  
99   },
```

```
100  {
101    "title": "Ludee",
102    "email": "datenzentrum@rl-institut.de",
103    "object": "metadata",
104    "comment": "Create table with updated data structure",
105    "date": "2022-02-11"
106  },
107  {
108    "title": "Ludee",
109    "email": "datenzentrum@rl-institut.de",
110    "object": "metadata",
111    "comment": "Update to OEMetadata version 1.5.0",
112    "date": "2022-02-11"
113  },
114  {
115    "title": "Ludee",
116    "email": "datenzentrum@rl-institut.de",
117    "object": "metadata",
118    "comment": "Update to OEMetadata version 1.5.1",
119    "date": "2022-02-15"
120  },
121  {
122    "title": "Ludee",
123    "email": "datenzentrum@rl-institut.de",
124    "object": "metadata",
125    "comment": "Add data annotation",
126    "date": "2022-10-04"
127  }
128 ],
129 "resources": [
130   {
131     "profile": "tabular-data-resource",
132     "name": "model_draft.rli_dea_td_generation_wind_turbine",
133     "path": "https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/view/
134           model_draft/rli_dea_td_generation_wind_turbine",
135     "format": "PostgreSQL",
136     "encoding": "UTF-8",
137     "schema": {
138       "primaryKey": [
139         "id"
140       ],
141       "foreignKeys": [],
142       "fields": [
143         {
144           "name": "id",
145           "description": "Unique identifier",
146           "type": "serial"
147         },
148         {
149           "name": "model",
150           "description": "Model name",
151           "type": "text"
152         },
153         {
154           "name": "scenario",
155           "description": "Contains information about technology data
156             and year, beginning from 2015 until 2050",
```

```
155     "type": "text"
156   },
157   {
158     "name": "region",
159     "description": "Region to which the data applies",
160     "type": "text"
161   },
162   {
163     "name": "type",
164     "description": "Type of wind turbine",
165     "type": "text",
166     "valueReference": [
167       {
168         "value": "onshore",
169         "name": "onshore wind farm",
170         "path": "https://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeo/
171           OEO_00000311"
172       },
173       {
174         "value": "offshore",
175         "name": "onshore wind farm",
176         "path": "https://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeo/
177           OEO_00000308"
178     }
179   ]
180 },
181 {
182   "name": "year",
183   "description": "Reference year",
184   "type": "integer",
185   "isAbout": [
186     {
187       "name": "year",
188       "path": "https://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeo/
189         UO_0000036"
190     }
191   ]
192 },
193 {
194   "name": "generating_capacity",
195   "description": "Generation capacity for one unit of the
196     technology",
197   "type": "real",
198   "isAbout": [
199     {
200       "name": "declared net capacity",
201       "path": "https://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeo/
202         OEO_00230002"
203     }
204   ],
205   "unit": "MW"
206 },
207 {
208   "name": "full_load_hours",
209   "description": "Average annual full load hours of the
210     technology",
211   "type": "integer",
```

```
206     "isAbout": [  
207       {  
208         "name": "full load hours",  
209         "path": "https://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeo/  
           OEO_00140144"  
210       }  
211     ],  
212     "unit": "h"  
213   },  
214   {  
215     "name": "nominal_investment",  
216     "description": "Nominal investment of the technology",  
217     "type": "real",  
218     "isAbout": [  
219       {  
220         "name": "investment cost",  
221         "path": "https://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeo/  
           OEO_00020167"  
222       }  
223     ],  
224     "unit": "M EUR/MW"  
225   },  
226   {  
227     "name": "rotor_diameter",  
228     "description": "Rotor diameter of the wind turbine",  
229     "type": "integer",  
230     "isAbout": [  
231       {  
232         "name": "rotor diameter",  
233         "path": "https://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeo/  
           OEO_00020144"  
234       }  
235     ],  
236     "unit": "m"  
237   },  
238   {  
239     "name": "hub_hight",  
240     "description": "Hub hight of the wind turbine",  
241     "type": "integer",  
242     "isAbout": [  
243       {  
244         "name": "hub height",  
245         "path": "https://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeo/  
           OEO_00140000"  
246       }  
247     ],  
248     "unit": "m"  
249   }  
250 ]  
251 },  
252 "dialect": {  
253   "decimalSeparator": "."  
254 }  
255 }  
256 ],  
257 "metaMetadata": {  
258   "metadataVersion": "OEP-1.5.2",
```



```
259   "metadataLicense": {
260     "name": "CC0-1.0",
261     "title": "Creative Commons Zero v1.0 Universal",
262     "path": "https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/"
263   }
264 },
265 "_comment": {
266   "metadata": "Metadata documentation and explanation (https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oemetadata)",
267   "dates": "Dates and time must follow the ISO8601 including time zone (YYYY-MM-DD or YYYY-MM-DDThh:mm:ss±hh)",
268   "units": "Use a space between numbers and units (100 m)",
269   "languages": "Languages must follow the IETF (BCP47) format (en-GB, en-US, de-DE)",
270   "licenses": "License name must follow the SPDX License List (https://spdx.org/licenses/)",
271   "review": "Following the OEP Data Review (https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/data-preprocessing/blob/master/data-review/manual/review\_manual.md)",
272   "null": "If not applicable use: null",
273   "todo": "If a value is not yet available, use: todo"
274 }
275 }
```

Listing 3.1: Metadata string for the onshore wind energy dataset

3.5.2 Using the data in REMix

To integrate the datasets in the REMix model, an automated routine was implemented in Python that downloads the data stored on the OEP and registered on the DataBus before converting the data into the REMix specific format. Subsequently to the download of the data, a mapping by means of a dictionary filters out the required parameters and translates them according to the REMix term. The REMix data structure expects the parameters to be separated. For example, the economic (see table 3.3) and technical parameters are read into the model from different tables, making an assignment necessary. Before a custom framework function can convert the dataset into the required tabular format, the data must be transformed and put into a python multi-index pandas dataframe with a specified index order. Finally, the data is stored in the designated folder so that it can be automatically recognized and read in by the model.

3.5.3 Using the data in FINE

The ETHOS.FINE framework offers a set of classes that act as source, sink, conversion, storage, or transmission components instead of predefined technologies. Therefore, it can also be applied to problems outside of Energy Systems Analysis. The form of the input data depends highly on the modeled system and the input arguments inside the model script use general terms for the mentioned classes. The user can decide how to organize the input data and read it into the model components. Nevertheless, the use of the Databus has the

indicator	accNodesData	converter_techs	vintage	amorTime	perUnitBuild	useAnnuity	perUnitTotal
Investment	Europe	nearShore	2015	25.0	2500.0	1.0	0.000
			2020	27.0	1750.0	1.0	0.000
			2030	30.0	1660.0	1.0	0.000
			2040	30.0	1600.0	1.0	0.000
			2050	30.0	1580.0	1.0	0.000
OMFix	Europe	nearShore	2015	0.0	0.0	0.0	51.570
			2020	0.0	0.0	0.0	36.053
			2030	0.0	0.0	0.0	34.250
			2040	0.0	0.0	0.0	32.880
			2050	0.0	0.0	0.0	32.538

Table 3.3: REMix input dataset created from economic data of exemplary wind turbine dataset retrieved from the OEP.

clear advantage of explicit definitions and documented provenance for input data inside the model script. Components in ETHOS.FINE usually require a string, number, pandas.Series or pandas.DataFrame as input arguments. For this demonstration a Python script has been used that queries records from the Databus and combines it with values from the Open Energy Ontology into a pandas.DataFrame. It establishes the metadata context to the OEO that resides under `ontology_uri` with

```
metadata_context = MetadataContext(ontology_uri)
```

and then creates a pandas.DataFrame from the Databus record under `file_id` with

```
df = metadata_context.gen_dataframe(file_id).
```

The labels from the raw data are replaced with the information from the OEO (`rdfs:label`) that is used as column title in the resulting pandas.DataFrame. It would also be possible to annotate and convert units or add additional explanations to the data in this step. Further, this method allows to change the Databus record from another source without changing the data processing for the model. If the new data source contains the same information as the previous one, the mapping to the OEO labels should be identical. The script and further explanations can be found under the LOD-GEOSS repository⁴ under “databus-snippets/table-metadata-mapping”.

⁴<https://github.com/LOD-GEOSS/databus-snippets/tree/master/table-metadata-mapping>

4 Publication and Discovery of Scenario data

4.1 Challenges

A typical challenge for users of scenario data is the search for data sets containing rather specific contents, e.g. time series on low temperature heat consumption in the industry sector in a country. Users of such data typically either need to browse several dedicated data platforms or, when using more general search engines, they need to find exactly those search strings which by chance are literally contained in the published data sets. The known obstacle that different redundant terms are used for the same content, leads to unsuccessful or inefficient searching. Combining several terms in an “and” search string can multiply this effect. From the view of the publishers of data sets the findability of their products is lower than it could be and the impact of the research content generated with considerable amounts of resources stays below its potentials.

4.2 Demonstrator: Publication and Search

The use case “Publication and Search” is defined to demonstrate the improved findability of scenario data sets through the Databus and metadata annotation concept. The storyline and action items of the use case are illustrated in figure 4.1. The use case takes the perspectives of the persons involved: of the publishers seeking for a high findability of their data sets, and of users searching for specific data contents.

In the use case, a person A in figure 4.1 (blue background in the figure) has published a scenario data on energy use in Germany in different sectors and related greenhouse gas emissions on a dedicated data platform. Here, the real life example of the climate protection scenario “Klimaschutzszenario 80 (KS80)” (Repenning et al. 2015) published on the Open Energy Platform (OEP) is chosen¹. On the OEP, the KS80 scenario consists of data tables containing the quantitative time series which form the content of the scenario. A metadata file for each data table containing information on the properties of the KS80 scenario and the respective data table has been made available by the publisher when uploading the KS80 scenario data tables on the OEP. So far, the databus and Open Energy Ontology (OEO) are not involved in publishing this data set. On the other side, person B (green background in figure 4.1) is searching for existing scenarios on greenhouse gas emissions (GHG). More specifically, he is searching for scenarios on GHG emissions of the cement industry in Germany

¹<https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/view/scenario?query=&tags=185>

Figure 4.1: Use Case Publication and Search

up to 2050. For person B, the scenario shall serve for comparison of different levels of ambition regarding defossilization processes of the cement industry. Accordingly, a so-called ”-80%” GHG” scenario is required for these purposes, describing a net total emission reduction of 80% of greenhouse gases until 2050 compared to 1990 for Germany. Obviously, a corresponding data set has been uploaded by person A on the Open Energy Platform. However, a large number of publication platforms, data bases and even individual sites e.g. of research institutes exist and may or may not contain the scenario data desired by person B. As, of course, search engines exist person A starts a search with the term ”GHG emissions” on the off chance. The KS80 data tables as well as the metadata file available on the OEP in parts contain the term ”CO2 emissions” rather than ”greenhouse gas emissions” or ”GHG emission”. Trial and error on the search string could of course yield a hit on an existing database. Yet, the databus involving the OEO annotation principle shows one of its key advantages, the increased findability of datasets: With the registration of the KS80 data sets in the data bus (see white background in figure 4.1), the KS80 data table reference here gets annotated with metadata on the databus. This metadata - other than the original KS80 metadata uploaded on the OEP - is mapped to the corresponding OEO terms (classes). The key terms or strings in the search of person A are ”greenhouse gas emissions”, ”cement industry”, ”Germany”, ”2020 - 2050” and ”-80 percent GHG”. On the other side, there are the corresponding terms contained in the tables of KS80 and the KS80 metadata file on the OEP. While terms like ”cement” appear identically in both, the KS80 and the OEO, other parts of the search string in this example occur in deviating forms, though mostly constituting synonyms. In the LOD-GEOSS demonstrator ”Publication and Search”, for the above shown use case, the registration on the databus, the annotation of the corresponding databus metadata with OEO classes, the inclusion of the necessary OEO classes therefore and the searching mechanism with finally yielding the databus reference for the requested KS80 data table have been implemented and applied.

4.3 Workflow

The data table 4.1² with the CO₂ emissions contains several columns. The first column is an id, the second column indicates the variable, the third the source category, the fourth is a code for the source categories in the Common Reporting Format³, the fifth is the unit, the sixth the year and the seventh column finally contains the value. The task of the demonstrator is to find a table with the variable "CO₂ Emission" and the source category "Cement production". To improve the discoverability of this table, it should be annotated with the Open Energy Ontology.

id	variable	source_category	crf	unit	year	value
1	CO2 emission	Cement production	2A1	kt	2020	120.341.729.645.945
2	CO2 emission	Cement production	2A1	kt	2030	110.348.953.001.713
3	CO2 emission	Cement production	2A1	kt	2040	100.761.960.331.264
4	CO2 emission	Cement production	2A1	kt	2050	93.782.514.117.748
5	CO2 emission	Lime production and use	2A2	kt	2020	49.678.558.106.972
6	CO2 emission	Lime production and use	2A2	kt	2030	4.898.786.616.731
7	CO2 emission	Lime production and use	2A2	kt	2040	48.975.776.219.463
8	CO2 emission	Lime production and use	2A2	kt	2050	48.752.992.170.988
...

Table 4.1: Excerpt from the KS80 scenario table on CO₂ emissions of industrial processes

The columns "variable" and "source category" with its contents therefore need to be linked to the Open Energy Ontology. The columns can be described with `isAbout:` tag, the contents with the `ValueReference:` tag. The version 1.5.1 and above of the OMETADATA can be used for that. The Metadata needs to be enhanced in the resources section. This is shown in the listings 4.1 and 4.2. In listing 4.1 in line 46 the variable is linked to the concept of a variable in the Open Energy Ontology. A variable is defined in the OEO class OEO00000435 and is "an information content entity that represents a changeable value, vector, matrix or function within a mathematical expression." The possible values of this variable are explained from line 49 as `ValueReference`.

```

1 [...]
2
3 "resources": [
4   {
5     "profile": "tabular-data-resource",
6     "name": "ksz2050_r2_ks80_co2_emissions_industrial_processes",
7     "path": "https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/view/scenario
           /ksz2050_r2_ks80_co2_emissions_industrial_processes",
8     "format": "PostgreSQL",
9     "encoding": "UTF-8",
10    "schema": {
11      "primaryKey": [

```

²https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/view/scenario/ksz2050_r2_ks80_co2_emissions_industrial_processes

³<https://unfccc.int/documents/461946>

```
12     "id"
13   ],
14   "foreignKeys": [
15     {
16       "fields": [
17         "year"
18       ],
19       "reference": {
20         "resource": "schema.table",
21         "fields": [
22           "year"
23         ]
24       }
25     }
26   ],
27   "fields": [
28     {
29       "name": "id",
30       "description": "Unique identifier",
31       "type": "serial",
32       "isAbout": [
33         {
34           "name": "dc:identifier",
35           "path": "http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/identifier"
36         }
37       ]
38     },
39     {
40       "name": "variable",
41       "description": "Variable",
42       "type": "string",
43       "isAbout": [
44         {
45           "name": "variable",
46           "path": "http://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeo/
47             OEO_00000435"
48         }
49       ],
50       "valueReference": [
51         {
52           "value": "CO2 emission",
53           "name": "CO2 emission value",
54           "path": "http://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeo/
55             OEO_00260008"
56         }
57       ]
58     }
59   ]
60 }
61 ]
62 [...]
```

Listing 4.1: Description of the variable in the metadata string.

The same is done for the source categories. The source category is linked to the OEO concept with `isAbout` from line 5 in listing 4.2. The `ValueReference` from line 11 links the cement production to the Open Energy Ontology.

```
1 {
2   "name": "source_category",
```

```

3   "description": "Source category (subsector of industrial
4     processes)",
5   "type": "string",
6   "isAbout": [
7     {
8       "name": "has source",
9       "path": "http://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeo/
10      OEO_00000528"
11    }
12  ],
13  "valueReference": [
14    {
15      "value": "Cement production",
16      "name": "CRF sector (IPCC 2006): cement production",
17      "path": "http://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeo/
18      OEO_00010165"
19    },
20    {
21      "value": "Lime production and use"
22    }
23  ]

```

Listing 4.2: Description of the source categories in the metadata string.

The updated OEMetadata string can now be published on the databus as it is described in section 8.2. Once the data is registered, it can be discovered with the MOSS as it is described in subsection 8.3.2.

Figure 4.2 shows that the sheet from the KS80 scenario can be found by using the OEO class OEO00010165 in the MOSS search tool.

The screenshot shows the Databus-MOSS search interface. The search term is "CO2 emission value". The search results are displayed in a table with columns for Title, Download, Comment, Databus ID Type, Start Date, and End Date. The search results include a list of suggestions and a table of results.

Title	Download	Comment	Databus ID Type	Start Date	End Date
Test Title	https://energy.databus...	This a short abstract fo...	FILE	2000-01-01T00:00:00+...	2030-01-01T00:00:00+...
Projections of CO2 em...	https://energy.databus...	https://www.oeko.de/...	ARTIFACT	2020-01-01T00:00:00+...	2050-01-01T00:00:00+...

Figure 4.2: MOSS search results for the cement class from the Open Energy Ontology

5 Exchanging annotated data in a Model workflow

This chapter shows how the various components of the distributed database infrastructure can be used to properly interpret previously created power system analysis datasets and make them reusable for new model experiments. The approach presented here is based on a scientific workflow in which the individual model calculations are indirectly coupled with each other by means of a data exchange via the databus.

5.1 Challenges

Exchanging data between models is often very cumbersome. Models have to analyze which data can be provided by the first model, which is usable by the second model. Then modelers start to define a specific data exchange for this particular coupling of models for a specific research questions. The developed solution can often only be used once for this specific task. In this described approach of a dedicated model coupling, the work is done by collaboration of the developers. If a second model wants to reuse data of a first model, which has been produced some time ago, e.g. in some previous project, it might become even more difficult, as the first model cannot be rerun to produce some specific output or the developer has already been gone to a different job. The data may be very hard to interpret and to reuse, if the data is not properly documented.

Using an open exchange platform with well defined and documented data can ease this task. If data is consistently annotated, it will be much clearer what a dataset contains and if it is (re-)usable for a specific research question. A good model workflow should have the following characteristics

- Easy to use API and integration in own modeling workflow
- Interpretation of their content/metadata (download)
- Transformation of their formats/resolutions (pre and post processing)
- Metadata annotations (choice of metadata schema and ontology)
- Upload of data (choice of database)

With this demonstrator we want to find requirements for data workflows in energy systems analysis.

An exemplary research question in the field of energy systems analysis serves as a use-case for the methods developed in the LOD-GEOSS project. The goal was to analyse power market prices for future energy system pathways which

were calculated with two different energy system model frameworks. While the energy system models use an optimisation approach to calculate the techno economic optimum of the future energy system design, the electricity market model uses a simulation approach to calculate realistic power market prices. The analysis requires the coupling of the two model types that focus on different modelling aspects. Results from the energy system model runs are fed into the electricity market model. Two energy system models were used in this workflow to demonstrate how the harmonized data between models can be shared and documented and to have the possibility to compare model results. This chapter describes the models/frameworks and their input and output parameters.

5.2 ETHOS.FINE

The ETHOS.FINE model framework has already been described in section [3.2](#).

In a simplified example application, three model runs for different years have been conducted to calculate the optimal system design and operation for every year in a green field energy system optimization. It has to be noted, that a green field approach does not take into account existing components at the beginning of the year. Furthermore, the model years are independent from each other. This leads to a theoretical supply optimum based on the technology assumptions for the given year. It does not reflect potential expansion pathways for the energy system. Design and operation of the generation components are passed to the power market simulation AMIRIS in order to deduct power market prices for the given design of the energy system.

5.3 TIMES

TIMES ([Blesl 2014](#), [Korkmaz et al. 2020](#)) is an economic model generator which is used with TIMES PanEU for German and European applications. The model provides a technology-rich basis for representing energy dynamics over a time horizon from 2010 to 2050. It is used for the analysis and optimisation of the entire energy sector which is driven by the end use energy service demands (e.g. train transport, residential lighting, high temperature heat requirement in the steel industry, etc.) for each region. Moreover, estimates of the existing stocks of power plants, transportation means, industrial plants, and the features of available future technologies are stored in the database, in addition to present and future sources of primary energy supply and their potentials. Finally, the model optimises the overall system cost to supply the required energy services and provides the investment and operation decisions as well as the energy trade within the model regions.

TIMES PanEU takes as input parameters the end use energy service demands as actual and projected values, the techno-economic characteristics of the technologies in the end use sectors and energy supply sector and several constraints for processes or commodities. Two of the most important constraints are the emission constraint which limits the overall greenhouse gas emissions to a certain climate target and the potentials constraint, which limits the potential

capacity or potential production of the renewable energy technologies in specific regions according to their potential available land area and weather conditions. The underlying data was fed into the model from the ENSPRESO (Ruiz et al. 2019) dataset according to workflow protocol. Further the time variation curve of electricity production from PV and wind power technologies was taken as an Input from the ENSPRESO dataset. The climate target and the emission constraint was equally harmonised between the TIMES and FINE model.

Typical output parameters of TIMES PanEU are the electricity generation and the capacities of public and industrial power plants, the final energy consumption of different energy carriers of different end use sectors, the primary energy consumption and the sector specific emissions. Beneath the activity and the capacity of technologies like power plants, their specific costs can be exported as an output parameter. For the model coupling workflow the installed capacities and electricity generation of public power plants for different technologies, the total electricity consumption in a hourly resolution time series as well as variable and fix costs of wind and PV power plants were provided as input parameters for AMIRIS.

5.4 AMIRIS

AMIRIS (Schimeczek et al. 2023) is an agent-based wholesale electricity market model for Germany. The model allows studying the impact of energy policy instruments on the economic performance of power plant operators and marketers. The model has an hourly resolution and computes wholesale electricity prices endogenously based on the simulation of strategic bidding behavior of prototyped market actors. This bidding behavior does not only reflect marginal prices, but it also considers effects of support instruments like market premia. Hence, AMIRIS focuses on the perspective of the actors within the energy system, their interactions and competition. Uncertainties of the actors (e.g. amount of the market premium or feed-in of renewables) can be explicitly considered and reflected in the strategies. Each agent may have its own goal and can be defined with its own decision-making rules. Traders, for example try to maximize their profits. Other agents provide functions to the simulations – e.g. the energy market clearing is provided by an energy exchange agent. In this way, the energy system can be simulated component by component and actor by actor. In AMIRIS, the modelled electricity sub-markets are calibrated and validated with a fundamental approach for the merit-order model using empirical data in the classical sense. The day-ahead spot market model has been validated for different years (2008, 2012-2016) in order to be able to make robust statements about electricity price developments.

AMIRIS takes as input time series for the various agents. In our particular case this means data from TIMES for one particular run and FINE for another. Independently from these models, these inputs include historical electricity prices for the energy exchange, the demand as well as potentials and costs for renewables and prices and costs for conventionals. Its main output is the future electricity price and the profitability of agents.

Figure 5.1: Model workflow to demonstrate the exchange of annotated data using an example research question from the research field of energy systems analysis.

AMIRIS has several outputs. Most notably, it produces the electricity prices calculated from the requested and awarded bids of the traders. It also outputs the market-driven CO₂-emissions and CO₂-prices as well as information about all agents in the simulation. Moreover, the output allows to calculate several indicators like the curtailment per technology, the volatility of the electricity price, its trend, the number of hours with negative or maximum prices, the energy not served and the total system cost.

5.5 Workflow

The workflow pictured in figure 5.1 starts with the selection of data to be harmonized between the energy system models FINE and TIMES, since both models operate on very different temporal and spatial resolutions and use different inputs. A second step consists in ensuring that both models use the data in the same way. This includes specifying the concept, but also to provide the units. In AMIRIS, this is facilitated by the coding convention that each variable has to bear the unit in its name. If metadata exists, this makes this process a lot less time-consuming. Finally, the data has to be downloaded. According to file format, resolution and units, these data need to be pre-processed, so that each model can use it as input. If done by hand, this is by far the most time-consuming step. As a third step, the models themselves are run. Again, the resulting data has to be changed according to the needs of the coupled model, the post-processing. A fourth step is to annotate the data with metadata, choosing a suitable metadata scheme and, preferably, using ontology concepts. This requires, as done in this project, that all model terms are part of the ontology. For that, the model vocabulary has to be spelled out separately, cleaned, discussed and the missing concepts suggested for discussion and implementation in the Open Energy Ontology. The metadata scheme is also from the Open Energy Platform. In a fifth step, this data is uploaded to the Open Energy Database (OED), so that the next iteration can be automated via scripts. The necessary adjustments in the models have been done, so that this step was successful. Models like AMIRIS now accept standardized input from the OEDB. This allows, in a sixth step, to easily replace data input from other models, thus making comparisons much easier. Hence, the robustness of

results is greatly increased. As a last step, the AMIRIS results can be enriched with metadata and uploaded themselves to the OEDB.

5.6 Assessment and interpretation of workflow results

While the input of TIMES and FINE have been harmonized by using the EN-SPRESO dataset, there are two separate workflows - TIMES coupled with AMIRIS and FINE coupled with AMIRIS. The input and the scenarios of all models are real data and represent valid assumptions of the energy system. However, since the focus of this project was to demonstrate an automated, annotated workflow, no further harmonization of input data between models was done. As a consequence, the results are not robust results that could be analyzed further. For example, both workflows (TIMES as well as FINE) produce very high electricity prices in AMIRIS that reflect a scarcity of electricity production with other periods of times where there is a surplus of production, hence very low (negative) electricity prices. This oscillation does not reflect real-market prices and is not seen in other AMIRIS-runs with validated and calibrated data.

6 Merging GEOSS Data and OEP Technology data for Evaluating Probabilistic Forecasts

6.1 Challenges

Renewable energy forecasting gets increasing importance in the operation of renewable energy systems. The results of complex ensemble forecast need to be evaluated with energy systems models. ProPower is a tool for such evaluations. For a proper set up it needs wind forecasts which can be found in the GEOSS system and information about transmission grids, wind turbine characteristics and demand/consumption which can be found on the Open Energy Platform. This demonstrator shows how these data sources are combined to parameterize a ProPower evaluation model in the NorthWest of Germany.

6.2 ProPower

ProPower ([Schyska 2022](#), [Buller 2023](#)), the Probabilistic Power Forecast Evaluation Tool has been developed at DLR in the recent years. The main purpose of ProPower is to assess the value of probabilistic power forecasts for PV and wind power systems compared to the usage of deterministic forecasts that do not contain any uncertainty information. Conclusively, it is possible to test and rank different probabilistic forecasts, either post-processed ones or issued by different NWP centres. Usual approaches to derive the cost-optimal power dispatch within a market or grid region under constraints (e.g. grid capacities) do not account for the potential balancing costs arising from forecast errors in wind and solar. It has been shown by ([Morales et al. 2014](#)) for a quite simplistic network (i.e. two nodes) that dispatch decisions based on pure deterministic forecasts lead to sub-optimal market clearing. To overcome this issue they proposed a stochastic market clearing model. In their model, average balancing costs are estimated from a set of scenarios of renewables feed-in that are equivalent to ensemble members from an ensemble prediction system. The ProPower tool is capable to simulate more complex power system (networks). ProPower is only restricted by the computational expenses of the optimization problem. A second market clearing that is based on updated forecasts of higher skills has been implemented.

Currently, ECMWF ensemble forecasts ([Leutbecher & Palmer 2008](#)) are used for the day-ahead market clearing and the intraday market clearing. The amount of required balancing is determined by the deviation of forecasted renewables feed-in to feed-in computed from ERA5 reanalysis. ProPower com-

putes the total costs of power generation which are the sum of costs for market clearings plus the costs for balancing. It has been shown that costs are lower when uncertainty information is included and better forecasts are used in the second market clearing (intraday).

As described in the application section on ProPower, the used networks are still very simplistic to analyze the behavior of ProPower in detail. In the coming months real-world networks will be setup to study the impact of improvements in short-term RES forecasting.

6.3 Wind data

In the GEOSS Portal (www.geoportal.org) new interesting data from Numerical Weather Forecasting for wind energy application has been spotted that is provided by ECMWF. Namely, wind speed components in 200 m height are newly available for the high resolution model (deterministic forecast) and for the Ensemble Prediction System (EPS). With increasing hub heights in the recent years, the introduction of 200 m winds is very useful. In particular, when considering to use future wind energy deployment scenarios. However, intensive browsing of the GEOSS Portal but also the original data archives at ECMWF, was not successful to find the corresponding 200 m winds in the ERA5 Reanalysis. Reanalysis data is often used to verify NWP forecasts in case observations are not available. Further research in the documentation of ERA5 revealed that 200 m wind are not foreseen in the ERA5 production. Conclusively, it is only possible to use the well established 100 m winds, in case it is intended and required in the application to verify short-term forecasts.

6.4 Workflow Application on ProPower

While ProPower was developed, the code was tested intensively with a 2-node example network with fictive network components. During the LOD-GEOSS project the network (power system) has been extended using the OEP. By intention it was envisaged that the new network is still rather simple to analyze the behavior of ProPower in detail. The aim has been to build a network in the North-West of Germany including the North Sea, as offshore wind energy needed to be included. It was agreed to design a 5-node network with three connected offshore wind farms. The OEP provided very valuable consumption (load) data on the level of Federal States of Germany divided in the sectors private domestic, CTS (commerce, trade, service) and industry. The data for the federal states have been put in a Pandas Data frame for further usage with

- `import pandas as pd`
- `df = pd.read_json('https://openenergy-platform.org/api/v0/schema/demand/tables/ego_demand_federalstate/rows')`

The total load data of Hamburg was used as reference for each considered node in terms of multiples. E.g. the node Ruhrgebiet was set 10 times the

Hamburg total load. However, for the split into sectors data from the OEP for North-Rhine Westphalia was used. With the same procedure the sectoral load for nodes in Emsland, Wilhelmshaven and Buettel have been retrieved for the sample network.

Furthermore, the OEP has been used to select an appropriate wind power curve to compute wind power for the selected application case. A vast set of turbine power curves is available at https://openenergy-platform.org/api/v0/schema/supply/tables/wind_turbine_library/rows.

As it was not intended to design a real-world application case, the Vestas V164, 9500 turbine was selected which represents a wind turbine that is still quiet rare but will be erected more frequent in the future. The power curve was retrieved in a Pandas Data frame with

- `import pandas as pd`
- `df = pd.read_json('https://openenergy-platform.org/api/v0/schema/supply/tables/wind_turbine_library/rows')`
- `vestas_v164_9500 = df[df['id'] == 131]`

in order to allow fast conversion into wind power using the existing short-term wind power forecasts and ERA5 reanalysis data for validation.

7 Reproducible modeling workflow on oemof-B3

7.1 Challenges

As long as there is only one modeler working with an energy system model, all modeling tasks could be performed locally. This is rarely the case, due to the complexity of modeling exercises. Transparent, comprehensible and collaborative workflows are needed for a sound scientific modeling process.

7.2 oemof-B3

The energy system model oemof-B3¹ is a sector-integrated model for the region Brandenburg/Berlin. It represents several sources, conversion, storage and transmission of several energy carriers: Electricity, central and decentral heat, hydrogen, CO₂ and methane.

The purpose of oemof-B3 is to generate results for model based scenarios of future energy supply with increasing share of renewable energies. The results of an individual model run are a cost-optimal system design and operation. The model has originally been developed in the project UMAS, building on previous work².

The app builds upon a data pipeline (snakemake) to support reproducibility of all modeling steps (data preparation, optimization, post-processing, plotting).

7.3 Workflow

The workflow integrates the following tools:

- snakemake
- oedb
- oemetadata
- oeo
- OEMetaBuilder
- Review process
- oem2orm / omi

¹(add citation - if citation.eff - ı put in <https://www.overleaf.com/project/6474bd1735da758c28ade497>)

²<https://github.com/rl-institut/appBBB>

- databus

The registration of the data’s metadata in the databus enables other researchers to better find the modeling data and results.

7.4 Results

Here, we present results and lessons learned from a applying the tools.

The sketch of the data pipeline shows the tasks of the snakemake workflow. The rules marked in red have been added to the pipeline.

Figure 7.1: Model pipeline

In summary, the following workflow has been applied:

The licenses of raw input data have been checked manually. The license check revealed some non-open licenses. Thus, the raw input data couldn’t be published as a datapackage with an open license on the OEP. The data remains in the model_draft, a section on the OEP for unfinished data of any kind. Metadata for raw input data was created manually using OEMetaData v1.5.1³. The metadata version control and review was performed on GitHub⁴. The ontological metadata annotation was done with help of the OEMetabuilder⁵. The input data was uploaded to the OEP⁶. Additionally the raw input data was registered on the databus⁷. Model results were uploaded to the OEP⁸.

³<https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oemetadata/blob/develop/metadata/v151/template.json>

⁴<https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/data-preprocessing/pull/106>

⁵<https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/oemetabuilder/>

⁶https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/view/model_draft?query=&tags=219&tags=364&tags=365

⁷https://energy.databus.dbpedia.org/chrwm/LOD-GEOSS_use_case_oemof-B3/

⁸https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/view/model_draft?query=oemof-b3&tags=263

7.5 Discussion and conclusion

Benefits of augmenting the existing data pipeline would be firstly to potentially reduce errors in data model of model-own assumptions and secondly to upload of results helpful for collaborative modeling. It would save computational time by preparing the resources once and then load them from a database.

Drawbacks could be identified. Changes in raw assumptions that affect resources are not tracked, therefore it is unclear when to update the resources on the database. The upload of unstructured raw data from external sources did not appear possible - strictly speaking: Data had to be adapted to fit the requirements of SQL tables.

We identify four lessons learned and recommendations:

1. Metadata creation takes a lot of time when performed in retrospective. Especially when the metadata is created by multiple people that don't have the data insight of the person who collected the data. Additionally people creating metadata need to be briefed on dtypes and postgresql naming conventions when the metadata is meant for upload on the OEP. This will reduce the workload when checking for metadata correctness in the data review process. Therefore, we advise to create metadata when collecting the data to ensure high metadata quality and thus increase the chance for reusage.
2. Raw data coming from external sources cannot usually be uploaded to oedb without changing them. One reason for this is that the conventions for database tables in SQL demand column headers to be renamed. More adaptations become necessary depending on the format of the data. Therefore, the data that can be uploaded are not raw are no proper input for a fully reproducible pipeline. The adaptations will have to be repeated once there is a newer version.
3. On the other hand, raw data that represent model-own assumptions can be collected in a structured schema already. Sharing and collaboratively updating data via the oedb has a strong benefit over e.g. sharing files. Future work on use cases can give more concrete advise and tools on organising this process and avoid version conflicts or accidental changes of data types.
4. Uploading of structured input data (resources) that consist of own assumptions and processed external data is recommended. It allows to license the data collection under an open license.

8 Data upload, annotation and download for the application

As it could be seen in the various demonstrators, some of the tasks in using the data infrastructure appear in a similar way. These tasks are therefore collected in this chapter. Typical tasks are:

- **Publication of data:** Structuring data to ease annotation, describing the data with the OEMetadata string, uploading the data to the OEP and finally registering the data on the Databus.
- **Searching and using data:** Use the search functions of the Databus or the Metadata Overlay System (MOSS), identify the data, download the data and integrate it into a model workflow.

This chapter describes publication of data on the Open Energy Platform (OEP) or Open Energy Database (OEDB) first. Then the data on the OEP is registered to the Databus. The third section describes the search of data and how it can be used in modeling.

8.1 Data Repository: Upload onto the Open Energy Platform

There are different ways to upload CSV-data to the Open Energy Platform¹ (OEP). These will be described in the following section.

Important: The OEP only accepts data in the CSV format. Since it is based on a relational database, it is possible to reference columns across tables with pairs of foreign keys.

8.1.1 Web interface

The easiest way to upload data to the OEP is to use the web interface, especially if only a few data sets need to be uploaded and a script-based workflow would create too much additional workload. The steps are straightforward:

1. Click on **Database** to enter the data section of the OEP.
2. Click on **Add data set** and **Create new table** to go to the upload page. You need to manually create all columns that your CSV file contains (it

¹<https://openenergy-platform.org/>

is useful to have a table with less columns than rows).

3. Insert column names and column data type (e.g. varchar for a sequence of characters) and define one column as primary key. Click on **Create table** to create your table in the database.

4. Go to the next section **Upload CSV** and select the CSV for upload on your local machine. Once done, the CSV columns are matched to the table you created in the previous step. Click on **Upload** to upload your CSV.

5. Once you have uploaded your CSV file, you can edit the table's metadata

within the web interface by filling out the provided form. The form is connected to the Open Energy Ontology and fields as **subject:** or **is About:** include a search function for the ontology once you start typing in the respective fields. Alternatively, you can use a prepared metadata file by pasting it at **Edit raw JSON**. For the preparation of your metadata file, a description of the OEP-Metadata-String² and an example JSON file³ can be found in the OEP-Repository.

The screenshot shows a web form for creating metadata. The form includes the following fields and options:

- Name:** A file name or database table name. Example: oep_metadata_table_example_y151
- Title:** A human readable full title including author. Example: Example title for metadata example - Version 1.5.1
- Id:** A Uniform Resource Identifier (URI) that unambiguously identifies the resource. This can be a URL or a DOI. Example: http://openenergyplatform.org/dataset/view/model_draft/oep_metadata_table_example_y151
- Description:** A description of the package. It should be usable as summary information for the entire package that is described by the metadata. Example: Example table used to illustrate the metadata structure and meaning
- Language:** A dropdown menu with a plus sign.
- An array:** A radio button option with a list of terms: wind rotor, wind energy converting unit, wind farm, wind energy.
- Subject:** A radio button option with a list of terms: wind, wind farm, wind energy.
- Referenc:** A radio button option with a list of terms: wind energy, onshore wind farm.
- Sub:** A radio button option with a list of terms: wind energy, onshore wind farm.
- Search:** A search input field with the text "wind" entered. Below it, a dropdown menu shows "wind" as a selected option. The text below the dropdown reads: "The class label (name) of the ontology term." and "Path".

Important: When using the JSON upload for metadata, the arguments in `foreignKeys` have to be deleted (set to: `[]`) from the metadata string if not used to reference in between tables, otherwise the upload fails. This is a known bug and will be corrected in the future.

6. Click on **Submit** to register your metadata on the OEP.

Expected result: Your table should be visible in the `model draft` section of the OEP.

Potential problems: You are using the JSON-Metadatasring and get an error when submitting the table. Make sure that you use the same format as the given example and that you have removed `foreignKeys` arguments if you do not want to use them.

Suggestion for improvement: Replace manual with automated input of CSV header as column names (feature request to OEDB has already been submitted).

8.1.2 Python API

An alternative to the upload via the web interface, it is possible to use a Python API. Especially for large data sets with a lot of columns it is advisable to use

²<https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oemetadadata/wiki/>
³<https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oemetadadata/blob/>

a Python script instead of the web interface. You can find a tutorial on the upload via Python API⁴ in the OEP-repository.

An alternative to create rich OEMetadata within Python based workflows is the tool `ioprocmeta`⁵ on PyPi. This tool can be used to write metadata into a variable within the workflows and finally save a OEMetadata JSON file with the data once it is written to disk. This output can be used to submit data to the OEP and to register the data there.

8.2 Register Data Source on Databus

Data saved on the OEP or any other data repository can be registered and annotated on the Databus platform⁶. Registration is possible either via a WebUI⁷ or the HTTP REST API⁸. For the latter, a wrapper in form of a Python library⁹ exists that makes it easy to annotate and deploy existing data sets.

Once the data is registered it gets a Databus identifier which has a fixed syntax:

```
https://domain.tld/user/group/artifact/version/
```

The identifier can be used a persistent id to reference a data set. The meaning of the single elements are:

- **user:** This is the registered user name of the user at the Databus. Therefore all identifiers on the database are referenced with a distinct user. It may be useful to create institutional accounts, if data should be rather associated with institutions than a certain person.
- **group:** Groups can be used to structure different datasets. The group may be a department of an institution, or a project or a model the data belongs to.
- **artifact:** This is the actual dataset. It should be short descriptive name for the data.
- **version:** Datasets can have different versions, as they e.g. get updated. Using the data of publication in the form YYYY-MM-DD is common way for naming versions of dataset.

8.2.1 Register via the WebUI

For manual registration an entry within the Databus must be created first. This needs an account for the databus which can be created via the "Login" button on the top of the page.

⁴https://openenergyplatform.github.io/academy/tutorials/upload/11_beginners_guide/

⁵<https://pypi.org/project/ioprocmeta/>

⁶<https://databus.dbpedia.org/>

⁷<https://databus.dbpedia.org/app/publish-wizard>, account required

⁸<https://databus.dbpedia.org/api/>

⁹<https://pypi.org/project/databusclient/>

The Upload link can be found beside the user icon. There is small drop down menu for editing the profile, add collections, publish data and logout.

”Publish Data” takes you to the ”Publish Wizard”. In the wizard with the group info, either a new group can be created or an existing group can be used. A group name is required which will be part of the URL for the data set later, a human readable title, an abstract and description of the group. The abstract can be generated from the description.

Figure 8.1: Group info in the Databus publish wizzard

Next is the information about the actual data artifact. It again needs a name which will be part of the URL for the data set, a human readable title, an abstract, and a description.

Figure 8.2: Artifact info in the Databus publish wizard

Each artifact has a version, which needs to be described next. For version names there are presets to e.g. use the current date as a version number.

License information needs to be added next. This field is linked to <https://dalicc.net> to include only machine readable licenses. The license information

Figure 8.3: Version info in the Databus publish wizard

is complemented by a short description on how to attribute the data and from which data it was derived from. Here URL, e.g. the Databus identifiers from the source data should be added.

Finally, the file names needed to be added as URLs. Variants can be added, e.g. if an artifact exists in multiple languages.

Once all fields have been filled out, the metadata can be published under a CC0 1.0 license. The publication creates a Databus identifier of the type <https://energy.databus.dpbedia.org/user/group/artifact/version> which is used in the next steps for annotation (see 8.2.3).

Expected result: The dat set is registered and visible on the databus.

Potential Problem: The manual filling of table is a labor intensive work and should only be used to register a few data sets. The API is recommended to regularly submit new data.

8.2.2 Register data using an API

An example implementation of using the API can be found in the databus-snippets repository¹⁰ called `databus_api_example.py`¹¹. If your data is registered on the OEP, you can use the script `oep_databus_api_registration.py`¹². For the use of the script, it is necessary to be a registered user of the databus. The user account can be created at the databus homepage. The single result tables can be grouped in the databus. For example, in the scenario results form model X as their group name and the single result or data tables are called artifacts.

By modifying the variables in the last part of the script (starting with account name, group, artifact) a dataid can easily be generated and deployed, similar to

¹⁰<https://github.com/LOD-GEOSS/databus-snippets>

¹¹https://github.com/LOD-GEOSS/databus-snippets/blob/master/databus_api_example.py

¹²https://github.com/LOD-GEOSS/databus-snippets/blob/master/oep_metadata/oep_databus_registration.py

the WebUI. Create a Python environment that contains all listed dependencies and run it from the command line interface. You can find further details on other uploading methods in the databus-snippets repository.

Expected result: The script returns the code 200 if everything worked as expected. It also returns the URL to the created entry.

Potential problems: If you use space characters for the artifact or group names the script is not working.

8.2.3 Annotation

The Databus platform gives us the opportunity to annotate data sets with terms from the Open Energy Ontology¹³ (OEO), as it is described in the reports "Distributed Data Infrascture" (Frey et al. 2023).

There are two ways to annotate the data:

1. Annotation of Databus identifiers with simple RDF identifiers.
2. Annotation of Databus identifiers with complete RDF Metadata graphs.

The simple RDF annotation is accessible via the MOSS interface through the menu item "Annotate". The databus identifier needs to be inserted into the top field, then the page shows the already existing annotations on the left-hand side. On the right-hand side, new terms can be searched from the Open Energy Ontology. You can browse all available OEO labels on the TIB Terminology Service¹⁴.

The complex annotation uses OEMetadata as a (sub-)graph which gets attached to the Databus identifier. This can be accessed via "Submit Metadata". The OEMetadata needs the added Context information, as described in Chapter 6 of the report "Distributed Data Infrascture" (Frey et al. 2023).

The OEMetadata can be added using the Metadata Overlay Search System (MOSS)¹⁵. On the left hand side there is an entry for "Submit Metadata". Here, the Databus identifier from the previous step needs to be entered in the first field and an OEMetadata string either in JASON-LD or Turtle needs to be copied to the second field. Once the submit button is pressed, the additional metadata gets linked to the Databus entry.

Alternatively, the OEP metadata string can also be submitted programmatically by sending a HTTP PUT request with the JSON as data and the Databus Identifier as an URL parameter to the REST API endpoint¹⁶.

¹³<https://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeo>

¹⁴<https://service.tib.eu/ts4tib/search?ontology=oeo>

¹⁵<https://moss.tools.dbpedia.org/>

¹⁶Example for this process can be seen here: <https://github.com/LOD-GEOSS/databus-snippets/blob/feature/oep-databus-registration/moss.py>

Figure 8.4: Submission form for OEMetadata in the MOSS Tool

8.3 Find and Download Data from Databus

There are two ways to search data on the Databus infrastructure, directly on the Databus and via the Metadata Overlay Search System (MOSS).

8.3.1 Searching on the Databus

The Databus User interface offers a search field on its starting page. Free text search terms can be entered here and the data fields which have been entered to the Databus as described in section 8.2 (titles, abstracts and descriptions of groups, artifacts and versions) will be used for searching. The search is just a simple full text search. Figure 8.5 shows a sample search for wind turbine data.

Figure 8.5: Searching on the Databus itself.

Clicking on a search result, e.g. the "RLI - Danish Energy Agency - Tech-

nology Data....” will take you to the information about the data. An example is in figure 8.6. The results page will show you the e.g. the available versions of the data and the files. The files can be directly downloaded from here.

The screenshot shows a web interface for a data catalog. The main heading is "RLI - Danish Energy Agency - Technology Data for Generation of Electricity and District Heating - Technology Data Catalogue for Electricity and district heating production - Updated April 2020 - Wind Turbine (Selected Parameter)". Below this, there is an "ABOUT" section and a "VERSIONS" tab. The "VERSIONS" tab displays a table of available data files.

Version	Variant	Format	Compression	Download
> 2022-10-12	---	zip	none	3 KB
> 2022-10-12	---	csv	none	2 KB

Figure 8.6: Search result on the Databus. Available versions and files can be seen here. A direct download is also available.

8.3.2 Advanced Search in the MOSS

In addition, there is the possibility to use the the search function of the MOSS system¹⁷ to find data sets based on OEO classes (or others) referenced in the annotated OEP metadata.

Search functionality can be found at the search tab of the MOSS page. The search field can be used to enter free text search terms. In a first step, the entered search term will be looked up in various ontologies, which are connected to the search portal. An example search is shown in figure 8.7. The right-hand windows shows possible ontology terms which could match the entered search term. By clicking on the "+", the terms can be added to the selected search terms.

Below is a field which defines the actual search in the graph of the Databus. The search type "VOID" searches in the metadata generated by the databus, "Annotations" searches within the simple annotations as described in subsection 8.2.3, "OEP_Metadata" searches in the graphs that were added by the OEMetadata annotations. The search terms in the left-hand box can be combined by "OR" or "AND". The search can also be applied to different Databus instances, which are listed in the drop-down menu. Figure 8.8 shows the search configuration part.

Pressing the search button results in a list of possible data sets as it can be seen in figure 8.9. The links to the data can be directly used to download the

¹⁷<https://moss.tools.dbpedia.org/search>

Figure 8.7: Searching ontology terms in the MOSS search

Figure 8.8: Search configuratoin of the MOSS search

data files.

Title	Download	Comment	Databus ID Type	Start Date	End Date
OEP Group	https://energy.databus...	OEP Group holds data...	GROUP		
RLI - Danish Energy A...	https://energy.databus...	This Technology Data ...	FILE		
Wind Turbine Library	https://energy.databus...	A collection of the mo...	FILE		
Wind Turbine Library	https://energy.databus...	A collection of the mo...	ARTIFACT		
Wind Turbine Library	https://energy.databus...	A collection of the mo...	FILE		

Figure 8.9: Example search results from the MOSS

8.4 Using the structured schema information in importing data

One of the advantages of OEMetadata annotated tables is the structured description of the table schema within the metadata information. This can be used to load a table e.g. from the OEP and to create a Pandas Dataframe where the columns can be referenced by Open Energy Ontology keys. With the integration of data sources within modeling workflows in mind, a Python interface has been developed that is able to download data into a Pandas Dataframe with annotations from the Open Energy Ontology¹⁸.

To download the data within a script two steps are required:

¹⁸<https://github.com/LOD-GEOSS/databus-snippets/tree/master/table-metadata-mapping>

8.4.1 Step 1: Generate the MetadataContext

Initiate an object of the class with

```
metadata_context = MetadataContext(ontology_uri).
```

This will provide the functionality for combining the Databus with mods (See section 2.3 in "Distributed Data Infrastructure" (Frey et al. 2023) and the given ontology. Parameters:

- **ontology_uri**: The URI of the ontology. Note that the FULL RDF content needs to be available from there.
- **metadata_endpoint**: SPARQL endpoint where the metadata (in context with the Databus Identifier) is stored. Default is the mods metadata endpoint.

Example: Load the context of the Open Energy Ontology from Archivo:

```
metadata_context =
MetadataContext("https://archivo.dbpedia.org/download?
o=http%3A//openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeo/&
f=ttl&v=2021.05.03-181314")
```

8.4.2 Step 2: Generate a pandas Dataframe of a file on the Databus

A data frame of a certain file on the Databus can be generated by calling

```
df = metadata_context.gen_dataframe(file_id).
```

Currently the mapping behavior is hard-coded to replace column titles with the labels of the Ontology based on the `isAbout` annotations. The Parameters are:

- **file_id**: an URI of a file on the Databus (see above).
- **column_infos** (Optional): If the metadata of the columns need to be used multiple times (e.g. for different versions of the same file) they can first be generated by calling `column_infos = metadata_context.get_columns_from_databus(file_id)` and passed by calling `df = metadata_context.gen_dataframe(file_id, column_infos=column_infos)`.
- **lang** (Optional): Use a language constraint on the values returned from the ontology. Default is "en".

Example: Generate a data frame of the turbine data deployed to the Databus:

```
gen_dataframe("https://databus.dbpedia.org/denis/
lod-geoss-example/api-example/2021-05-10/
api-example_type=turbineData.json")
```


9 Best practices

9.1 Using shared data

Step 1: Reorganize data to be data base compliant

The first step in successfully sharing data is to reorganize the data to be database compliant. An Example on how to reorganize data can be seen in tables 3.1 and 3.2 in section 3. All the labels need to be column headers and the single data sets are rows of the table.

Step 2: Enhance the Open Energy Ontology with the relevant terms

In order to able to annotate the data set with proper definitions, the column labels should correspond to concepts in the Open Energy Ontology. The open Energy Ontology can be searched within the OEO Viewer¹ or by downloading the ontology and searching it with the tool Protege. This is described in the contributing.MD² of the Open Energy Ontology. A third option is to use the Metadata generator of Steps 3 which can also search the Open Energy Ontology.

If a suitable term is not found in the ontology, a new term needs to be defined. To do this, follow the procedure described in the contributing.MD³ of the Open Energy Ontology or go through the appropriate modules of the Open Energy Academy⁴

Step 3: Annotate your data with the OEMetadata String and Upload it to the OEP

Once the data is transformed into a suitable structure in step 1 and all the concepts are found in the Open Energy Ontology in step 2, the data can be annotated by the Open Energy Metadata⁵. Either the JSON string can be edited in a text editor, based on a template or by the OE Metabuilder⁶. Tools like ioprocmeta⁷ can help to create metadata directly within processing scripts. The metabuilder has the advantage that it can search the Open Energy Ontology directly and therefore facilitates the association of the right classes to the data columns.

¹<https://openenergy-platform.org/viewer/oeo/>

²<https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/ontology/blob/dev/CONTRIBUTING.md>

³<https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/ontology/blob/dev/CONTRIBUTING.md>

⁴https://openenergyplatform.github.io/academy/courses/05_ontology/

⁵<https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oemetadata/tree/master>

⁶<https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/oemetabuilder/>

⁷<https://pypi.org/project/ioprocmeta/>

Once the metadata has been completed, the data and the metadata can be uploaded to the Open Energy Database. This is described in detail in section 8.1.

The data does not always need to be uploaded to the Open Energy Platform. If it should reside on a different repository, which is accessible by the Databus, it can also be registered in STEP 4 from there. The actual data file and the meta data need to be accessible by the data bus for it.

Step 4: Register data in the Open Energy Databus

Finally, the data needs to be registered to the databus to make it findable by the search tools. This is described in section 8.2.

Step 5: Convert data into model input

Use Tools like the table-metadata-mapping in section 8.4 to convert data into your data input.

9.2 Publish scenario data

Step 1: Collect data and reorganize data to be database compliant

The first step in scenario publication is the collection of the relevant data sheets which belong to a scenario data set. Reorganize the data if necessary for the single tables to be database compliant. An example of how to transform data tables is given in the Chapter 3 "Using shared Data".

Step 2: Annotate the single data tables with OEMetadata and Upload it to the Open Energy Platform.

All the data tables need to be annotated with OEMetadata. This can be done by using the OEMetabuilder⁸ on the Open Energy Platform or by creating the JSON files directly.

If column headers are not found in the Open Energy Ontology, they need to be introduced into the OEO according to the procedure described in the contributing.MD⁹.

The Metadata can also be created by uploading the data sheets to the Open Energy Platform as described in section 8.1.

If not done in the previous steps, the data needs to be uploaded to the Open Energy Platform as described in section 8.1 or another suitable repository.

As the `subject:` tag in the OEMetadata is an array of objects, multiple subjects can be entered. To be sure that the scenario can be found, make sure that e.g. the relevant technologies or sectors are referenced in the `subject:` tag.

⁸<https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/oemetabuilder/>

⁹<https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/ontology/blob/dev/CONTRIBUTING.md>

Step 3: Register data in the Open Energy Databus

Finally, the single sheets need to be registered to the databus to make it findable by the search tools. This is described in section 8.2.

Step 4: Create a Collection for the single sheets.

Once all the single sheets are registered in the databus, they can be bundled into a collection.

For this you need to create a collection for your data set. If you go to publish data on the Databus as described in 8.2 you will find a tab for your collections. If you click on manage collections, you get a list of your collections and option to create a new collection. The identifier will be part of the URL, the label is a human readable title. You can also add an abstract and a description of your scenario. Finally, you can commit your new collection.

There are two ways to add the single sheets to the collection. Either you go to the single files on the databus. On the top right of the single entry there is a small drop down menu. You can use to add this entry into a collection.

Figure 9.1: Drop down menu to add a data set to a collection.

As second option is to use the collection editor where you can add resources with their Databus identifiers. This is shown in figure 9.2.

Figure 9.2: Adding resources to a collection in the collection editor.

9.3 Exchanging Data in a Model Workflow

Step 1: Prepare output data, reorganize data

In order to be able to exchange data described with OEMetadata via the Databus, the data needs to be reorganized to be database compliant. The

data should be structured in a way so that all data labels appear as column headers and the data records are subsequent data rows. An example of how to transform data tables is given in the Chapter 3 "Using shared Data".

Step 2: Annotate data and publish it on a public repository

Next, the data needs to be annotated with OEMMetadata. This can be done by uploading the data to the Open Energy Platform. The creation of the OEMMetadata is part of the Upload process to the OEP, as it is described in section 8.1.

Alternatively, the OEMMetadata can also be created as part of the workflow by writing the JSON structure with the output data. This can be used to upload the results data via API calls to the OEP.

If the data is to be stored on a different repository, the OEMMetadata JSON file still needs to be created for the later registration on the Databus. The OEMMetadata Builder¹⁰ can help to create sample Metadata files, which can be adapted.

Tools as `ioprocmeta`¹¹ can help to create the OEMMetadata within Python scripts.

Step 3: Register the data on the Databus

Once the output data and the OEMMetadata documentation are ready, they can be registered on the Databus.

If the data is stored on the Open Energy Platform, the script `oep_databus_registration.py`¹² can be used to register the data from the OEP to the Databus.

If the data is stored elsewhere, the data can be registered as it is described in section 8.2.

Step 4: Download data, interpret it and create model input files

Once the Databus identifiers from the previous step are available, they can be passed to the consecutive model. The next model can derive the download link from the Databus identifier and download the data. This data can be parsed and used as input for the next model.

The download URLs from the data can e.g. be queried with curl:

```
curl -H "Accept:applicatoin/ld+json" https://energy.databus.dbpedia.org/
ludee/dea-technology-data/rli-dea-td-generation-wind-turbine/
2022-10-12
```

The resulting JSON file can be parsed for the download URLs.

The more generic approach would be to use tools like the `table-metadata-mapping`, as described in section 8.4. Here, the data can be downloaded and

¹⁰<https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/oemetabuilder/>

¹¹<https://pypi.org/project/ioprocmeta/>

¹²https://github.com/LOD-GEOSS/databus-snippets/blob/master/oep_metadata/oep_databus_registration.py

converted into a Pandas Dataframe. If the mappings of the Open Energy Ontology to the necessary input data are known, the data can be extracted from the data frame by the respective ontology keys. Here, the exact structure of the exchanged data gets less important, as the assignment of output of the first and input of the second model is done via the ontology keys.

Once the relevant input parameters are identified, they can be written into the input data of the second model.

Step 5: Document output data

Go back to step 1 for the documentation and publication of the output data of the second model to make it reusable for the next analysis.

9.4 Using GEOSS time series data

Step 1: Finding suitable GEOSS data

Use the GEOSS portal¹³ to search for data or take on the recommended data sets from the report "Using GEOSS and Copernicus for Energy Systems Analysis" (Hoyer-Klick et al. 2023).

Step 2: Download and convert data

As the GEOSS is less structured, the available data sets come in very different forms. Many reanalysis data set use the GRIB format, NetCDF is also quite common. Well documented data sets should come with some description of the data format which has been used for storage.

Data download and conversion is described in more detail for some of the usable data sets in the report "Using GEOSS and Copernicus for Energy Systems Analysis" (Hoyer-Klick et al. 2023).

9.5 Workflow Tracing

Step 1: Identify your input data

The first step in improving workflow tracing is to analyze the workflow of the modeling approach and identify all your input data. Ideally some or all of your data has already been documented with OEMetadata. If not, the input data should be documented with appropriate OEMetadata. Depending on the input data and its documentation, different levels of detail may be possible. If the input data is not database compliant, a more simple annotation without the schema description may be suitable.

Also check the licenses of the input data, if you are able to republish the data e.g. on the Open Energy Platform for increased transparency. If not, the data may need to stay in the non-public `model_draft` section of the OEP.

¹³<https://www.geoportal.org/>

Step 2: Register the input data in the Databus

Follow the the description of section [8.2](#) to register your input data on the Databus.

Step 3: Reference your input data in the model output

You can use the Databus identifiers from Step 2 in the "was derived from" field of the Databus registration and in the **sources:** section of the OEMetadata while documenting your output data.

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